

TRANSMISSION STUDIES ON *PHILAEENUS SPUMARIUS* AND CANDIDATE VECTORS OF *XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA* IN APULIA (SOUTHERN ITALY)

V. CAVALIERI^{1*}, C. DONGIOVANNI², D. CORNARA³, G. ALTAMURA², D. BOSCIA¹, F. PORCELLI³, D. BOSCO⁴, M. SAPONARI¹

¹CNR Istituto per la Protezione Sostenibile delle Piante (IPSP), SS Bari, 70126 Bari, Italy. ²Centro di Ricerca, Sperimentazione e Formazione in Agricoltura (CRSFA) "Basile Caramia", Locorotondo (Bari), Italy. ³DiSSPA Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro, Bari, Italy. ⁴DISAFA Università degli Studi di Torino, Grugliasco (Torino), Italy.

***Corresponding author: vincenzo.cavalieri@ipsp.cnr.it.**

Recent surveys, aimed at describing Auchenorrhyncha occurring in olive groves in the Apulian region (southern Italy), identified the presence of at least 15 Taxa, among which the most abundant was *Philaenus spumarius* (L.), the ascertained vector of *Xylella fastidiosa* strain CoDiRO. In this first year of the project, several transmission experiments were set in order to (i) evaluate the influence of olive cultivar on the efficiency of acquisition and transmission of *X. fastidiosa* by *P. spumarius*; (ii) assess the role of other Auchenorrhyncha species as vectors of the bacterium. For the first objective, three independent transmission tests were carried out under field conditions using infected trees of two highly susceptible cultivars: "Cellina di Nardò" and "Ogliarola", and trees of the tolerant cultivar "Leccino". Adult spittlebugs collected in the pathogen-free area, were caged on the branches of the selected infected trees for 48-72 hours of acquisition and then transferred (in groups of five) onto healthy young olive trees for 48h. All the insects that survived the transmission tests were collected and tested in qPCR for the presence of *X. fastidiosa*. The results show a significant difference in the acquisition, with only 6-8% of insects retaining the bacterium after feeding on the trees of the tolerant variety vs 38-40% of positive specimens after feeding on the susceptible olive trees. Although the assessment of the efficiency of transmission is ongoing, this result is expected to be related to the acquisition rates.

For the second objective, transmission tests have been conducted using adult specimens of *Anoplotettix* spp. and *Thamnotettix zelleri* (Cicadellidae), *Agalmatium* spp. (Issidae), *Cercopis sanguinolenta* (Cercopidae) *Neophilaenus campestris* and *P. italosignus* (Aphrophoridae), and *Cicada orni* (Cicadidae).

Preliminary results on their infectivity rate (under natural and/or experimental conditions) showed that the majority of the insects tested negative for *X. fastidiosa*, with few insects yielding results close to the detection threshold. Conclusive assessment regarding their capability and role in the spread of the bacterial infections will be obtained upon sampling and testing the receptor plants in the following 6-12 months.